

ASSIGNMENT

NEW ENCYCLOPÆDIA BRITANNICA (INFORMATION SOURCES AND SERVICES)

DEPT. OF LIBRARY SCIENCE AND INFORMATION SCIENCE
PANJAB UNIVERSITY CHANDIGARH

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P R E F A C E.

UTILITY ought to be the principal intention of every publication. Wherever this intention does not plainly appear, neither the books nor their authors have the smallest claim to the approbation of mankind.

To diffuse the knowledge of Science, is the professed design of the following work. What methods, it may be asked, have the compilers employed to accomplish this design? Not to mention original articles, they have had recourse to the best books upon almost every subject, extracted the useful parts, and rejected whatever appeared trifling or less interesting. Instead of dismembering the Sciences, by attempting to treat them intelligibly under a multitude of technical terms, they have digested the principles of every science in the form of systems or distinct treatises, and explained the terms as they occur in the order of the alphabet, with references to the sciences to which they belong.

As this plan differs from that of all the Dictionaries of Arts and Sciences hitherto published, the compilers think it necessary to mention what they imagine gives it a superiority over the common method. A few words will answer this purpose. Whoever has had occasion to consult Chambers, Owen, &c. or even the voluminous French *Encyclopedie*, will have discovered the folly of attempting to communicate science under the various technical terms arranged in an alphabetical order. Such an attempt is repugnant to the very idea of science, which is a connected series of conclusions deduced from self-evident or previously discovered principles. It is well if a man be capable of comprehending the principles and relations of the different parts of science, when laid before him in one uninterrupted chain. But where is the man who can learn the principles of any science from a Dictionary compiled upon the plan hitherto adopted? We will, however, venture to affirm, that any man of ordinary parts, may, if he chuses, learn the principles of Agriculture, of Astronomy, of Botany, of Chemistry, &c. &c. from the **ENCYCLOPEDIA BRITANNICA.**

IN the execution of this extensive and multifarious undertaking, the Compilers laboured under many disadvantages, partly arising from the nature of the work, and partly owing to the following circumstance.

THE

How to use the MICROPAEDIA

The 12 volumes of the MICROPAEDIA contain tens of thousands of shorter articles on specific persons, places, things, and ideas, arranged in alphabetical order. The MICROPAEDIA can be used as an information resource on its own; and it can function as support for the longer articles in the MACROPAEDIA (to which it refers whenever appropriate). The MICROPAEDIA in turn is supported by references in the INDEX and by the lists of suggested readings in the PROPAEDIA. Finally, the MICROPAEDIA is the portion of the *Encyclopaedia Britannica* best suited for the reader who wishes to browse among the countless subjects in all notes of human learning and history in all times and places.

Alphabetization

Entry titles are alphabetized according to the English alphabet, A to Z. All diacritical marks (such as in ò, ì, or ñ) and foreign letters without parallels in English (such as äyn [ʿ] and hamza [ʾ]) are ignored in the alphabetization. Apostrophes likewise are ignored. Titles beginning with numbers, such as 1812, War of, are alphabetized as if the numbers were written out (Eighteen-twelve, War of).

Alphabetization proceeds according to the "word-by-word" principle. Thus, Mount Vernon precedes mountain; any John entry precedes John Henry, which in turn precedes John's disease. Any character or string of characters preceding a space, hyphen, or dash is treated as a word and alphabetized accordingly. Thus, De Broglie precedes debenture, and jack-o'-lantern precedes jackal. Titles with identical spellings are arranged in the following order: (1) persons, (2) places, (3) things.

For many rulers and titled nobility, chronological order, as well as alphabetical order, governs placement. Rulers of the same given name (e.g., William) may be grouped together, separate from other entries, and indicated by the symbol •. They may be subgrouped alphabetically by country and, within each country, arranged chronologically (William I, William II, etc.). Nobility or peers of the same titled name (e.g., Essex, EARLS OF) are similarly grouped together, separate from other entries; they are indicated by the symbol • and arranged chronologically.

Places with identical names are arranged in the alphabetical order of the countries where they are located. Identical place-names in the same country are alphabetized according to the alphabetical order of the state, province, or other political subdivision where they are found.

Entry arrangement

The titles of entries are arranged according to the forms commonly found in indexes and dictionaries, with some special conventions.

Entry titles for certain physical features, institutions, structures, events, and concepts are ordinarily inverted to place the substantive word first. Thus, the Bay of Bengal is entered as Bengal, Bay of; the Bank of England as England, Bank of; the Tower of London as London, Tower of; the Siege of Vienna as Vienna, Siege of; and the balance of power as power, balance of. If the name of a physical feature, institution, structure, event, or concept has two or more descriptors, it is entered under the descriptor appearing first. Thus, the Episcopal Church in Scotland is entered as Episcopal Church in Scotland (not Scotland, Episcopal Church in); the Leaning Tower of Pisa as Leaning Tower of Pisa; and the kinetic theory of gases as kinetic theory of gases.

The entries for most Western persons are arranged so that one can read a name in correct order by beginning after the first comma, proceeding to the end of the boldface type, returning to the beginning word or words, and proceeding forward to the first comma. Thus, the entry March, Patrick Dunbar, 2nd Earl of, is read "Patrick Dunbar, 2nd Earl of March"; the entry Orléans, Louis, duc d', is read "Louis, duc d'Orléans." Names of Far Eastern origin are given in Oriental order, with the surname preceding the personal name (e.g., Tōjō Hideki, Deng Xiaoping, Nguyen Cao Ky).

Cross-references

Some cross-reference entries appear in the MICROPAEDIA for the purpose of leading a reader from names that are familiar to alternate names that may not be. Cross-references also appear frequently within or at the ends of standard entries, where they are identified by *see*, *see also*, *see under*, *q.v.* (*quod vide*, "which see"), or *qq.v.* (*quae vide*, "which see," plural).

Certain entries serve both as relatively brief essays on general subjects and as cross-references to the same subjects treated at greater length and in greater depth in the MACROPAEDIA. Such an entry (e.g., igneous rock) begins with a definition of the subject and then provides the following cross-reference: "A brief treatment of igneous rocks follows. For full treatment, *see* MACROPAEDIA: Minerals and Rocks."

Entries on certain broad subjects (e.g., music) direct the reader to several relevant articles in the MACROPAEDIA and also to the PROPAEDIA for listings of related articles in the MICROPAEDIA.

Abbreviations

Abbreviations used in the MICROPAEDIA are given in a list that appears at the end of every MICROPAEDIA volume.

Territorial boundaries

In articles and maps indicating disputed geopolitical boundaries and territories, the attribution of sovereignty or administrative subordination to any specific area does not imply recognition of the status claimed by an administering power.

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Accounting

The purpose of accounting is to provide information about the economic affairs of an organization. This information may be used in a number of ways: by the organization's managers to help them plan and control the organization's operations; by owners and legislative or regulatory bodies to help them appraise the organization's performance and make decisions as to its future; by owners, lenders, suppliers, employees, and others to help them decide how much time or money to devote to the organization; by governmental bodies to determine how much tax the organization must pay; and occasionally by customers to determine the price to be paid when contracts call for cost-based payments.

Accounting provides information for all these purposes

through the maintenance of files of data, analysis and interpretation of these data, and the preparation of various kinds of reports. Most accounting information is historical—that is, the accountant observes the things that the organization does, records their effects, and prepares reports summarizing what has been recorded; the rest consists of forecasts and plans for current and future periods.

Accounting information can be developed for any kind of organization, not just for privately owned, profit-seeking businesses. One branch of accounting deals with the economic operations of entire nations. The remainder of this article, however, will be devoted primarily to business accounting.

The article is divided into the following sections:

Company financial statements 1
 The balance sheet
 The income statement
 The statement of cash flows
 Disclosure and auditing requirements
 Measurement principles 2
 Asset value
 Asset cost
 Net income

Depreciation
 Cost of goods sold
 Problems of measurement
 Managerial accounting 3
 Budgetary planning
 Cost finding
 Cost and profit analysis
 Performance reporting
 Bibliography 5

COMPANY FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Among the most common accounting reports are those sent to investors and others outside the management group. The reports most likely to go to investors are called financial statements, and their preparation is the province of the branch of accounting known as financial accounting. Three financial statements will be discussed: the balance sheet, the income statement, and the statement of cash flows.

The balance sheet. A balance sheet describes the resources that are under a company's control on a specified date and indicates where these resources have come from. It consists of three major sections: (1) the assets: valuable rights owned by the company; (2) the liabilities: the funds that have been provided by outside lenders and other creditors in exchange for the company's promise to make payments or to provide services in the future; and (3) the owners' equity: the funds that have been provided by the company's owners or on their behalf.

The list of assets shows the forms in which the company's resources are lodged; the lists of liabilities and the owners' equity indicate where these same resources have come from. The balance sheet, in other words, shows the company's resources from two points of view, and the following relationship must always exist: total assets equals total liabilities plus total owners' equity.

Assets are ordinarily subdivided into current assets and noncurrent assets. The former include cash, amounts re-

ceivable from customers, inventories, and other assets that are expected to be consumed or can be readily converted into cash during the next operating cycle (production, sale, and collection). Noncurrent assets may include noncurrent receivables, fixed assets (such as land and buildings), and long-term investments.

The liabilities are similarly divided into current liabilities and noncurrent liabilities. Most amounts payable to the company's suppliers (accounts payable), to employees (wages payable), or to governments (taxes payable) are included among the current liabilities. Noncurrent liabilities consist mainly of amounts payable to holders of the company's long-term bonds and such items as obligations to employees under company pension plans. The difference between total current assets and total current liabilities is known as net current assets, or working capital.

A simple balance sheet is shown in Table 1. Because the two sides of this balance sheet represent two different aspects of the same entity the totals must always be identical. Thus, a change in the amount for one item must always be accompanied by an equal change in some other item. For example, if the company pays \$40 to one of its trade creditors, the cash balance will go down by \$40, and the balance in accounts payable will go down by the same amount.

The income statement. The company uses its assets to produce goods and services. Its success depends on whether it is wise or lucky in the assets it chooses to hold and in

Table 1: Any Company, Inc.: Balance Sheet as of Dec. 31, 20

assets		liabilities and owners' equity	
Current assets		Current liabilities	\$ 20
Cash	\$100	Wages payable	160
Marketable securities	50	Accounts payable	\$180
Accounts receivable	150	Total current liabilities	10
Inventories	180	Deferred taxes	70
Total current assets	\$480	Long-term bonds payable	\$560
		Total liabilities	
Long-term investments	70	Owners' equity	\$100
Pland and equipment		Common stock	150
Original cost	\$300	Additional paid-in capital	230
Less accumulated depreciation	110	Retained earnings	480
Total assets	\$740	Total owners' equity	\$740
		Total liabilities and owners' equity	\$740

How to use the PROPAEDIA

As its title indicates, the PROPAEDIA, or Outline of Knowledge, is intended to serve as a topical guide to the contents of the *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, enabling the reader to carry out an orderly plan of reading in any field of knowledge or learning chosen for study in some depth. The PROPAEDIA's table of contents gives the reader an overview of the Outline of Knowledge as a whole; the introductory essays for each of the ten parts illuminate the major concerns of that part of human knowledge; the headnotes that are affixed to parts and divisions prepare the reader for examination of the subjects being covered there; and the outlined presentations of these subjects, with their lists of related article titles, enable the reader to carry on a course of study that may be more or less extensive and detailed in accordance with individual interests and desires.

Structure. Each of the 10 parts, 41 divisions, and 177 sections that make up the PROPAEDIA is marked in the table of contents by a heading, which is followed by the number of the page on which that unit of the PROPAEDIA begins. This structure provides three ways to utilize the outline: (1) one may turn to any of the parts as a whole and examine the contents of that part; (2) one may select a particular division of a part and examine the contents of that division; or (3) one may focus on a single section or several sections of such a division and examine the contents of that section or those sections.

Sectional outlines. The sectional outlines present, in an orderly arrangement of topics, subjects that are treated in articles in the MACROPAEDIA and MICROPAEDIA. Each section number incorporates the numbers of the part and division to which it belongs. For example, Section 725 is the fifth section in Part Seven, Division II; Section 96/10 is the tenth section in Part Nine, Division VI. In each sectional outline the major subjects are indicated by

capital letters ("A," "B," etc.). There are always at least two major subjects, but there may be many more in a given section. When it is necessary to subdivide a major subject, up to three additional levels may appear in the outline; the first is indicated by Arabic numerals, the second by lowercase letters, and the third by Roman numerals, as shown below:

B. Metallurgy

1. Mineral processing: crushing and grinding of ores, concentration of metallic minerals
2. Extractive metallurgy: separation of metallic elements from mineral form
 - a. Pyrometallurgy: processes that involve the use of heat
 - i. Roasting: oxidizing, reducing reactions
 - ii. Smelting: processes for removing molten metal from molten slag

The INDEX, with its alphabetically arranged subject headings, is indispensable in finding where a given subject appears in the Outline of Knowledge. These headings, where appropriate, carry specific citations pointing to the part, division, or section of the PROPAEDIA that covers the subject in question. A subject referred to in a sectional outline is, in many cases, treated fully in an article of the same title in the MACROPAEDIA or MICROPAEDIA, each such title being included in the list of suggested reading at the end of the section. These titles, as well as significant references to the subjects in other contexts, are cited in the INDEX. It may be helpful to compare the functions of the PROPAEDIA and the INDEX: Both are guides to the contents of the *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, but the PROPAEDIA's primary purpose is to indicate what subjects are covered, while the INDEX's primary purpose is to indicate where they are covered.

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How to use the INDEX

The INDEX to volumes 1 to 29 begins on page 1 of this volume. The INDEX is the result of an accumulation of hundreds of thousands of references locating precisely the section of a page in which a person, place, thing, or idea is mentioned in any of the thousands of *Encyclopædia Britannica* articles. These references have been assembled, combined, edited, and alphabetized to make an INDEX of more than 700,000 references. This INDEX gathers together all the topics covered by the more than 40,000,000 words in the text, sorts them out, and tabulates them for much the same reason that roads and signposts are planned and built in an unfamiliar country.

Encyclopædia Britannica is so vast a work that it cannot be used to greatest advantage without first consulting the INDEX. For example, if readers turn to "United Kingdom" in Volume 29, they will find a long article, but this by no means represents all the information in *Britannica* about the United Kingdom. To find all of this material, readers must go to the INDEX, where, under the entry heading "United Kingdom," they will find not only the reference to the main article but also about 1,000 references to many related articles throughout the 29 text volumes of *Britannica*.

Or readers may wish to learn something about, say, human equality. If they look in MICROPAEDIA Volume 6 at the appropriate alphabetical position, they will not find an article on human equality. The INDEX, however, lists references to four articles in *Encyclopædia Britannica* in which information on human equality may be found.

Readers who turn to the INDEX first will use *Britannica* most intelligently and profitably. Because the purpose of the many thousands of INDEX entries is to classify, clarify, and search out specific information, much attention has been given to their simplification. Such clarity and simplification result in an index that is very specific, and the reader should remember this when seeking out information. The references subordinate to an entry heading pertain to that entry heading alone, whether it represents a thing, an idea, a person, or a place. For example, the references listed at "bird" contain information pertaining to birds as a class, and not to specific bird species. Generally, therefore, the reader should attempt to be as specific as possible when seeking information. For instance, a reader researching the flight of the sparrow should first look at the entry headings "flight" and "sparrow," and not "bird." The "see also" references at the bottom of an INDEX entry should be consulted as well, for they direct the reader to more specific topics. Only if such a search proves fruitless should the reader consult a more general entry heading.

When using the INDEX, the reader should also keep in mind that the INDEX employs different types of references. For example, under the INDEX entry "Flaubert, Gustav," one finds a reference to his literary style. While a volume, page number, and column are given in the reference (see the Index Rules below), one should not assume that only at that specific point in the text is there information concerning Flaubert's

literary style. The reader should feel free to look not only at the specific passage indicated in the subheading but also at the text surrounding that specific passage. For example, the discussion of Flaubert's literary style may continue for a number of paragraphs and even on to another page.

When a sustained discussion of a subject spans a number of paragraphs, or even a number of pages, the subheading will occur in the following form:

comparison with Saint Paul 16:258:1b *passim* to 262:1a

This indicates that the discussion of a subject continues for the duration of the passage indicated and that the entire reference should be read in order to gain the most information. When such a sustained discussion represents the most exhaustive reference on a particular topic in the entire *Encyclopædia Britannica*, the subheading will be placed directly below the entry heading and will occur in the following form:

major ref. in Biblical Literature 14:987:1a

Index Rules. Entry headings are set in boldface type, flush with the left-hand margin in a column; they are followed by an identifying phrase or word in parentheses. Entry headings for towns are followed by abbreviations giving the country, state, or other political subdivision in which the towns are situated. Names of lakes, rivers, and mountains are identified as physical features. Persons are often identified in parentheses by nationality or profession or both. Entry headings having identical spellings are usually followed by a parenthetical descriptive word or abbreviation.

If the INDEX entry has a corresponding article in the text, the volume and page number of that article immediately follow the entry heading and identifier, as in the following:

Flaubert, Gustave (Fr. au.) 4:821:3a

If an INDEX entry has two corresponding articles in the text, their references are listed directly below the entry heading as MICROPAEDIA and MACROPAEDIA and are followed by volume and page numbers. In such a case, map references will be listed below the text references, as will references to the BRITANNICA WORLD DATA. Such an INDEX entry will take the following form:

Togo, or Republic of Togo, or
République Togolaise
MICROPAEDIA 11:820:1a
MACROPAEDIA 29:909:2a
LOCATION MAP 29:794
STATISTICAL INFORMATION: see
BRITANNICA BOOK OF THE YEAR

Additional references below the entry heading refer readers to other articles containing information on the subject. These subheadings have a short phrase indicating the context in which the information will be found and are indented to indicate different levels of subordination. These subheadings also direct readers to illustrations in *Encyclopædia Britannica*.

to statistical information in the BRITANNICA BOOK OF THE YEAR, and to the PROPAEDIA section that broadly covers the subject in the outline of knowledge.

All references in an INDEX entry show the volume, page number, column of the page, and a letter "a" or "b" indicating the upper or lower half of the column. For example, 1:485:3b points to the MICROPAEDIA Volume 1, page 485, the third column of the page, and the lower half of that column.

In addition to containing entry headings that have volume and page references, the INDEX has thousands of cross-references. Cross-reference entries for alternative spellings and titles send readers to the main spelling or title. For example, the cross-reference "Constantinople: *see* Istanbul" means that all references with information about Constantinople will be listed under Istanbul. It is important to remember that cross-references in the INDEX refer only to other INDEX entries. Cross-references also allow the reader to gain access to more specific information. For example, there is a "*see also*" cross-reference at the bottom of the INDEX entry "bridge" that directs the reader to INDEX entries on related topics.

Alphabetization. The INDEX uses the word-by-word system of alphabetization (whereby a word is defined as one or more characters separated from the next one or more characters by a space). When one word differs from another only by the presence of additional letters at the end, the shorter word precedes the longer (*e.g.*, "gold" precedes "golden"). Entry headings consisting of more than one word are alphabetized among the single-word entries according to the first word, so that, for example, all of the entries starting with "gold" will be alphabetized in sequence. Entry headings having the first word in common (*e.g.*, "Gold Coast," "Gold Cup") will then be alphabetized among themselves according to the second word. Entry headings having three or more words in common follow the same principles.

Following is a set of examples:

gold
 Gold, Thomas
 Gold Coast
 Goldbach, Christian
 Goldbach conjecture
 Golden
 Golden Gate Bridge
 Goldenberg, Emmanuel

Diacritical marks do not affect alphabetization. If a diacritic is the only difference between two entry headings, the entry without the diacritic is first.

Hyphenated words (and words that are separated by en dashes [-]) are treated as two separate words, the hyphen (or dash) being treated as a space. Quotation marks that appear in titles of works are generally ignored in alphabetization. If the only difference between two entries is the presence of quotation marks in one, the entry heading without quotation marks is placed first.

Entry headings whose first characters are numerals are alphabetized as though the numbers were spelled out. The numerical components of entries are arranged according to their numerical value, from lowest to highest. For example:

Eight Immortals
 1812, War of
 Eighteenth Amendment
 Eightfold Path
 B-9
 B-17
 B-29
 B-52

Abbreviations for "Saint(s)" and its foreign-language equivalents (St., Sta., Ste., SS., etc.) are alphabetized as if they were spelled out.

Saint John
 Sainte-Beuve, Charles-Augustin
 SS. Peter and Paul, Cathedral of
 Sainsbury, George Edward Bateman
 Proper names having the prefix "Mac" or its contracted forms "Mc" and "M'" are all alphabetized as "Mac."
 McCarey, Thomas Leo
 M'Carthy, Sir Charles
 MacCarthy, Joseph Raymond
 MacCarthy Island

NEW ENCYCLOPÆDIA BRITANNICA

Evaluation:

AUTHORITY

Title	New Encyclopædia Britannica
Editor	Dale Hoiberg
Publisher	Encyclopædia Britannica, Inc.
Place of Publication	Chicago (USA)
Language	English
First Ed.	1768-1771
Latest ed. (15th)	1985-2010
Purpose	General

INTRODUCTION

Encyclopædia Britannica is the oldest English-language general Encyclopædia published in 1768. First Edition was 3-volume reference work, founded by Colin and Andrew Bell. Most of the articles were written by [William Smellie](#) and edited by Colin, who printed the pages. It is written by about 100 full-time editors and more than 4000 contributors, who have included 110 Nobel prize winners and five American presidents. The 2010 version of the 15th edition, which span 32 volumes and 32640 pages, was the last printed edition. In 1994 Britannica launched a website to become the first encyclopaedia on the internet.

SCOPE

- ✓ It provide timely, relevant and trustworthy information and instructional products for homes, schools, universities, libraries and workplaces around the world.
- ✓ The volumes are quite valuable for their up-to-date coverage of the new world geography. Example Russian Republic, etc.
- ✓ Encyclopædia Britannica is an excellent teaching aid because the articles on each subject area are complete with helpful supplemental references for further study.
- ✓ Encyclopædia Britannica aim to convey the important accumulated knowledge for their domain, such as an Encyclopædia of medicine, philosophy, law.
- ✓ Encyclopædia Britannica have 40 thousands articles.
- ✓ Encyclopædia Britannica cover topics on Animals, Art, Astronomy, +Science, Chemistry, Countries Of World, Earth, Government, Law, Politics, Health, History, Life, Biosphere, Literature, Math, Religion, Sports, Recreation Technology.
- ✓ Its content is international in scope.
- ✓ Information presented for a common reader.

TREATMENT

- ✓ Encyclopaedia Britannica is cross referenced, easy to use and comprehensive in its subject coverage.
- ✓ Table of contents at the beginning of long articles refer the readers find coverage of specific topics they are investigating.
- ✓ It provides access to a vast world of trusted and authentic knowledge and offers a wealth of interactive education in an easy manner.
- ✓ Population data for the united states, individual states, cities and towns based on 2000 census and of Canada from the country's 20001 census are provided.
- ✓ The style of encyclopaedia is general not specified.

ARRANGEMENT

It is alphabetically arranged according to word by word.

Index: It has 2 indexes in which first covers words from (A-K) and second covers from (L-Z). following is format in which we use this index.

For example: Togo

11 : 820 : 1a

Volume number : Pages : Parts

Where parts may be upper or lower half.

Abbreviations are used that too alphabetically.

The 7th to 14th editions included a maps volume.

In the 15th edition of encyclopaedia Britannica which was designed three parts:

1. **Micropaedia** (ready reference and Index): Tended to be short, specific and unsigned and were followed (until 1985) by index references to related content elsewhere in the set.
2. **Macropaedia** (Knowledge in Depth): It was greatly restricted with the amalgamation and regrouping of hundreds of articles.
- 3, **Propaedia**(Outline of Knowledge): Provided a tropical guide to the encyclopaedia as well as information about the contributors.

FORMAT

PRINT FORMAT

It is in 32 volumes.

Micropaedia has (1-12) volume, macropaedia has (13-19) volume , 1 Propaedia and (A-K) and L-Z) two indexes.

Hardcover binding

Good quality paper is used.

Printing is clear and legible.

ONLINE FORMAT

- ✓ Online version is more helpful as it is suitable for all age group of people especially kids. Encyclopædia Britannica Provides mobile app. Eg. Britannica kids apps, I- phone app, I-pad.
- ✓ What the fact (wtfact) tells us the defined fact on topic like the real science behind the Frankenstein, famous mustaches in history.
- ✓ A-Z quick search you can quickly search any topic or article by this feature.
- ✓ Online Quizzes series on various topics like not so common fact, Texas revolution , earth sciences.
- ✓ Demystified stories give insight into some of life's big mysteries , answers the question which are full of curiosity.

CD-ROM AND DVD

It is available in CD-ROM and DVD format. It is issued in 1994. Providing text and a dictionary, along with proprietary retrieval software, on a single disc, Featuring illustrations and photos; multimedia including videos, animations.

SPECIAL FEATURES

- ✓ **RSS FEEDS AND WIDGETS-** Enjoy rich Britannica encyclopaedia content conveniently delivered right to your browser or on your webpage.
- ✓ Color maps are accompanied by map indexes listing the major geographical features.
- ✓ **Newsletter-** Expand your knowledge with Britannica's newsletters. Britannica Editors have handpicked articles and content to give you new perspectives on today's hot topics.
- ✓ A new feature introduced Britannica Kids which is trustworthy, accurate, fact and safe. Where fun tools have also been provided, i.e. Educational games.

DRAWBACK

Encyclopædia Britannica is not available in printed form.

CONCLUSION

Encyclopædia Britannica is oldest and largest contemporary English Britannica. It covers all topics of knowledge. Britannica is known to be the authoritative source in almost any research topic. It is trusted sources and complete reference information is available. Online version is helpful for all. The last printed version is its 2010 edition.

REFERENCE

- ✓ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Encyclopaedia-Britannica-English-language-reference-work/Fifteenth-edition>
- ✓ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Encyclopædia-Britannica-English-language-reference-work/media/1/186618/140472>
- ✓ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Encyclopædia-Britannica-English-language-reference-work>
- ✓ <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smart-news/encyclopedia-used-be-spelled-Encyclopædia-because-letter-english-doesnt-have-anymore-180961328/>
- ✓ Encyclopaedia Britannica (Panjab University Library chandigarh)